

Dendrochronological analysis of timber found at Bjørvika B2 Oslo, Norway Project number 2016291

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Fifteen samples from timbers found during excavation at Bispevika B2 in Oslo were submitted for analysis. All samples are of conifer, and on microscopic examination, nine are found to be of *Pinus sp.*, pine while six are *Picea sp/Larix sp.*, spruce/larch. Fourteen of the samples are dated.

The results

The results of the dendrochronological analysis are described according to their contextual groupings.

Fig. 1. Bjørvika B2, Oslo, Norway. Dendrochronological dating of the timbers.

Context K8

Five samples are from context K8. They are all pine and all five are dated. Two samples are from a bulwark foundation (flåtestokk) and both have bark edge preserved. The outermost formed ring is fully formed on both, so the trees were felled in the trees' dormant season (winter). The trees that these two samples come from were felled in winter AD 1593-94 and winter AD 1594-95 respectively. The remaining three samples are from quay logs (bolverksstokk) and these also all have bark edge preserved. On two samples, it is possible to determine that the outermost ring is fully formed. The trees that these samples come from were felled in winter AD 1595-96 (see fig. 1).

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		N035002a	N035001a	N035005a	N035003a	N035004a	N035006a	N035009a	N035010a	N035007a	N035011a	N035008a	N035012ax	N035014a	N035015a
K8	P17 N035002a*		1,54	1,09	3,05	2,68	1,71-	-	-	-	-	-	\	2,79\	
	P15 N035001a	1,54*		3,51	2,48	2,25	2,51	1,29-	-	-	1,82	2,53\	-	-	\
	P18 N035005a	1,09	3,51*		5,28	3,82	2,38-	-	2,33	1,29	1,54	2,94\	-	-	\
	P16 N035003a	3,05	2,48	5,28*		5,27-	-	-	1,23-	-	1,16	2,99\	-	-	\
	P19 N035004a	2,68	2,25	3,82	5,27*		2,61-	-	2,14-	-	-	1,82\	-	-	1,41\
K7	P7 N035006a	1,71	2,51	2,38-	-	2,61*		1,82	3,16	1,97	1,69-	-	\	-	1,94\
	P10 N035009a	-	1,29-	-	-	-	1,82*		4,12	4,03	3,97	2\	-	-	2,16\
	P11 N035010a	-	-	2,33	1,23	2,14	3,16	4,12*		5,81	4,28	2,58\	-	-	2,08\
	P8 N035007a	-	-	1,29-	-	-	1,97	4,03	5,81*		3,35	4,23\	-	-	\
	P12 N035011a	-	1,82	1,54	1,16-	-	1,69	3,97	4,28	3,35*		3,49\	-	-	\
P9 N035008a	-	2,53	2,94	2,99	1,82-	-	2	2,58	4,23	3,49*		-	-	\	
K4	P1 N035012ay\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	*	2,54	2,94
	P3 N035014a	2,79-	-	-	-	1,41	1,94	2,16	2,08-	-	-	-	2,54*	3,32	
	P4 N035015a	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	\	2,94	3,32*	

Table 1. Bjørvika B2, Oslo. Result of the correlation between each dated tree-ring curve with each other, at their cross-matching position. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values. Filenames in orange are pine, those in blue, spruce.

The samples from context K8 cross-match as shown in table 1. An average of all five tree-ring curves has been made (N035m6_k8) of 141 years in length. As the correlation between this average and a range of tree-ring datasets for pine for Northern Europe shows (table 2), the material achieves the highest match with other pine chronologies from material from Oslo.

FileNames	-	-	N035m6_k8	
-	start	dates	AD 1455	
-	dates	end	AD 1595	
N_Oslo big pines	AD 1308	AD 1842	13,82	Norway Oslo big pines april 2016 110 timbers (Daly unpubl)
N0253M01	AD 1351	AD 1621	12,98	Oslo Bispevika B3B7 61 timbers (Daly 2016d)
k010301s	AD 1395	AD 1706	9.92	Gulphauser farmhouse Lr Saxony Swedish timber (Crone pers comm)
N029M001	AD 1308	AD 1569	9.59	Bispevika 2 bulwark caisse 35 timbers (Daly 2016c)
N022M001	AD 1457	AD 1595	9.29	Oslo DEG felt vest 7 timbers (Daly 2013)
N007m005	AD 1479	AD 1622	9.19	Barcode 11-13 Oslo Bolværk 22 timbers (Daly 2008)
B027pine C ...	AD 1484	AD 1642	9.06	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 5 timbers (Daly 2016b)
30530010	AD 1343	AD 1669	7.70	MK Skeppsholmen 36 series (Eggertsson pers comm)
NOMK0803	AD 1345	AD 1780	7.62	Norway Aust Agder (Bartholin pers comm)
APOTHCRS	AD 1382	AD 1666	7.26	Apothecaries Hall London 3 timbers (Bridge pers comm)
ToLQHS2	AD 1497	AD 1677	6.95	Queens House Tower of London pine 3 timbers (Bridge pers comm)
IMPORTx8	AD 1329	AD 1671	6.83	Scotland pine imports 59 timbers (Crone pers comm)
FYRSVEN1	AD 1513	AD 1636	6.56	Svendborg Norwegian pine (Bartholin pers comm)
Swed_mal	AD 1083	AD 1992	6.49	Malardalen Gotland Sweden (Alf Bräthen)
21014M01	AD 1380	AD 1576	6.33	Copenhagen B&W Grund 2 trees (Daly 1997a&b)
FORTHx6	AD 1329	AD 1619	6.27	Scotland pine FORTHx6 38 timbers (Crone pers comm)
SWED_STK	AD 1127	AD 1671	6.18	Stockholm/Uppland (Bartholin pers comm)
gbl01	AD 1504	AD 1719	6.15	London Camden St Georges Church Bloomsbury (Bridge pers comm)

Table 2. Bjørvika B2, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the average curve from the pine timbers from context K8 (N035m6_k8) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

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Context K7

Six samples are from context K7. All six samples are of spruce/larch, probably spruce. All six samples are dated.

Bark edge is preserved on five of the samples, and the outermost ring is fully formed, so the trees that these samples come from were felled in the winter or early spring. These trees were all felled in the same year, in winter AD 1616-17 (see fig. 1).

The tree-ring curves from the samples from context K7 cross-match as shown in table 1. An average is made from four of the tree-ring curves. (Two curves are not included in the average, as they both display very restricted growth resulting in a phase of very narrow tree-rings.) The average (N035m3_k7 spruce) is 56 years in length. The correlation between the average and a selection of chronologies for Northern Europe is shown in table 3. The trees for this construction were probably found in the Oslo hinterland.

Filenames	-	-	N035m3_k7 spruce	
-	start	dates	AD 1561	
-	dates	end	AD 1616	
20000059	AD 1488	AD 1647	6.61	Oslo Revierstr (Bartholin pers comm)
k010301s	AD 1395	AD 1706	4.95	Gulphauser farmhouse Lower Saxony Swedish timber (Crone pers comm)
B027pine C	AD 1484	AD 1642	4.93	Gammel Strand Copenhagen C orange 5 timbers (Daly 2016b)
N025K5&K6 M002	AD 1452	AD 1621	4.85	Oslo Bispevika B3 B7 K5&K6 4 timbers (Daly 2016a)
Z129F003	AD 1529	AD 1842	4.53	Deichman 6 timbers filtered (Daly 2015)
N007gran1	AD 1485	AD 1606	4.04	Oslo barcode spruce 3 timbers (Daly 2008 & 2010)

Table 3. Bjørvika B2, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the average curve from the spruce timbers from context K7 (N035m3_k7 spruce) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high *t*-values.

Context K4

Four samples are from context K4. They are all pine. Three of the samples could be dated. Bark edge could not with certainty be identified on any of the dated samples. The outermost preserved and measured tree-ring on sample P3 (N035014a) was formed in AD 1850, and an additional incomplete ring is observed outermost on this sample. The tree from which this sample comes was felled after AD 1851. The dating of the other two samples from this construction phase indicate a similar felling date.

The correlation between the three dated samples from context K4 is shown in table 1 and plots of these tree-ring curves are also examined visually. Due to very narrow growth phases in the tree-ring curve from sample P3 a version is made excluding the first 130 rings (N035014ax) for building the average. A shorter version is also made of the tree-ring curve from sample P1, also due to a period of very narrow growth (N035012ax). The average for context K4 (N035m4_k4) is 177 years long and covers the period AD 1674-1850. The correlation between this average and a series of tree-ring datasets for pine for Northern Europe is shown in table 4. The curve achieves its highest correlations with Norwegian datasets, and with material from Durham in England that we know to be imports from Scandinavia.

Filenames	-	-	N035m4_k4	
-	start	dates	AD 1674	
-	dates	end	AD 1850	
DURQSQ01	AD 1585	AD 1900	6.49	Durham Cathedral 11 timbers (C Tyers pers comm)
NOR_VISD	AD 1600	AD 1983	6.17	Visdalen Norway (Briffa et al 1986)
NOR_HOVD	AD 1645	AD 1954	5.73	Hovden S Norway 10 pines (Thun 1987)
NOR_JOND	AD 1605	AD 1981	5.71	Jondalen Norway (Briffa et al 1986)
SELTYP_P	AD 1424	AD 1938	5.65	Selbu & Tydal Norway Pine 13 trees (Eidem 1953)
30383999	AD 1437	AD 1987	5.43	Sweden Handöl (Bartholin pers comm)
TYDAL_P	AD 1527	AD 1936	5.40	Tydal Norway Pine 3 trees (Eidem 1953)
GROVAT_R	AD 1417	AD 1936	5.30	Grovatnet Pine 15 trees (Ording 1941)
NOR_EDM2	AD 1461	AD 1954	5.08	Norway spruce (Bartholin after Eidem 1953)
SELBU_P2	AD 1424	AD 1938	5.04	Selbu Norway Pine 9 trees (Eidem 1953)
50000002	AD 1319	AD 1856	4.91	Norway Oestlandet (Bartholin pers comm)
SWED023	AD 1107	AD 1827	4.48	Jamtland (Fritz Schweingruber)
99200010	AD 871	AD 1986	4.46	Norway south-east (Thun pers comm)
SWED_JM2	AD 1305	AD 1827	4.37	Jaemtland (Bartholin pers comm)

Table 4. Bjørvika B2, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the average curve from the pine timbers from context K4 (N035m4_k4) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Remarks

Using the number of sapwood rings to estimate the felling date in the absence of bark edge is highly problematical in pines, due to the wide variation in the number of sapwood rings. It can also be difficult to identify the sapwood edge in waterlogged archaeological conifer timbers. Sapwood has therefore not been recorded in this analysis.

For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t -value ("t-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed.

Literature

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Catalogue:

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	conversion	extra end	Average ring width mm	interpretation / felling
K8											
N035001a	Oslo B2 2016291 p15 k8 bolverksstok PISY	69	AD 1527	AD 1595	C	0	W	W	N	1,92	AD 1595-96 winter
N035002a	Oslo B2 2016291 p17 k8 bolverksstok PISY	57	AD 1539	AD 1595	C	0	W	W	N	1,87	AD 1595-96 winter
N035003a	Oslo B2 2016291 p16 k8 bolverksstok PISY	141	AD 1455	AD 1595	F	0	Y	W	N	1,12	AD 1595-96
N035004a	Oslo B2 2016291 p19 k8 flåtestok PISY	90	AD 1505	AD 1594	V	0	W	W	N	1,24	AD 1594-95 winter
N035005a	Oslo B2 2016291 p18 k8 flåtestok PISY	57	AD 1537	AD 1593	V	0	W	W	N	1,97	AD 1593-94 winter
K7											
N035006a	Oslo B2 2016291 p7 k7 sperrestok	106	AD 1510	AD 1615	C	0	N	W	N	1,14	after AD 1615
N035007a	Oslo B2 2016291 p8 k7 flåtestok	84	AD 1533	AD 1616	V	0	W	W	N	1,40	AD 1616-17 winter
N035008a	Oslo B2 2016291 p9 k7 flåtestok	53	AD 1564	AD 1616	V	0	W	W	N	1,95	AD 1616-17 winter
N035009a	Oslo B2 2016291 p10 k7 flåtestok	53	AD 1564	AD 1616	C	0	W	W	N	2,28	AD 1616-17 winter
N035010a	Oslo B2 2016291 p11 k7 flåtestok	56	AD 1561	AD 1616	C	0	W	W	N	2,46	AD 1616-17 winter
N035011a	Oslo B2 2016291 p12 k7 flåtestok	56	AD 1561	AD 1616	C	0	W	W	N	1,97	AD 1616-17 winter
K4											
N035012ay	Oslo B2 2016291 p1 k4 bolverksstok PISY	173	AD 1674	AD 1846	V	0	?	W	N	0,67	AD 1846?
N035012ax	Oslo B2 2016291 p1 k4 bolverksstok PISY	118	AD 1674	AD 1791	V	0	?	N	H55	0,85	Short version for calculating the average
N035013a	Oslo B2 2016291 p2 k4 bolverksstok PISY	75			V	0	?	W	N	1,72	Undated
N035014a	Oslo B2 2016291 p3 k4 bolverksstok PISY	307	AD 1544	AD 1850	V	0	N	W	H1	0,39	after AD 1851
N035014ax	Oslo B2 2016291 p3 k4 bolverksstok PISY	176	AD 1675	AD 1850	V	0	N	W	H1	0,30	Short version for calculating the average
N035015a	Oslo B2 2016291 p4 k4 bolverksstok PISY	135	AD 1716	AD 1850	V	0	N	W	N	0,79	after AD 1850
Averages											
N035m6_k8	Oslo Bjørvika B2 k8 5 timbers (p15, p16, p17, p18 & p19) PISY	141	AD 1455	AD 1595						1,61	
N035m3_k7 spruce	N035m3_k7 spruce 4 timbers (p9, p10, p11 & p12) PCAB	56	AD 1561	AD 1616						2,15	
N035m4_k4	Bjørvika B2 Oslo k4 3 timbers (p1, p3 & p4) PISY	177	AD 1674	AD 1850						0,58	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
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